

The Unjournal

Evaluation 2 of "Accelerating Vaccine Innovation for Emerging Infectious Diseases via Parallel Discovery"

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Summary Measures

We asked evaluators to give some overall assessments, in addition to ratings across a range of criteria. *See the evaluation summary “metrics” [link evaluation summary here] for a more detailed breakdown of this. See these ratings in the context of all Unjournal ratings, with some analysis, in our [data presentation here](#).¹*

	Rating	90% Credible Interval
Overall assessment	40/100	20 - 60
Journal rank tier, normative rating	2/5	1 - 3

Overall assessment: We asked evaluators to rank this paper “heuristically” as a percentile “relative to all serious research in the same area that you have encountered in the last three years.” We requested they “consider all aspects of quality, credibility, importance to knowledge production, and importance to practice.”

Journal rank tier, normative rating (0-5): “On a ‘scale of journals’, what ‘quality of journal’ should this be published in? (See ranking tiers discussed [here](#))” *Note: 0= lowest/none, 5= highest/best”.*

See [here](#) for the full evaluator guidelines, including further explanation of the requested ratings.

Footnotes

1. Note: if you are reading this before, or soon after this has been publicly released, the ratings from this paper may not yet have been incorporated into that data presentation. ↵